

ISic3067

I.Sicily inscription 3067

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

building

Material

limestone (blue-gray)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Soluntum

Place of origin (modern)

Solunto

Provenance

via dell'agora, in situ

Coordinates**Current Location**

TM 645420
EDR 136678
EDCS 64900502
PHI 332226

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 56.1102

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Portale, E.C. 2006. Problemi dell'archeologia della Sicilia ellenistico-romana: il caso di Solunto. *Archeologia Classica*. 57: 49-114. At 87-98 fig.24-25

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